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Abstract

The amount of Fission Products (FP) in the core is one of the key parameters driving the progression and the radiological consequences of a hypothetical postulated Severe Accident (SA) in a Nuclear Power Plant (NPP). The larger the mass of FPs loaded, the larger is the decay power, which triggers the accident after the reactor scram. Having this in mind, the effect of the employment of different amount of FPs should be considered in the analysis of a hypothetical SA.

The current report focusses on the evaluation of the fuel inventory at different burn-up states in the integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) Design-1 and Design-2 in the framework of the work activities of the Task 2.3 of the WP2 (SCENARIOS) of the SASPAM-SA project. With this goal, depletion calculations have been performed at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT, Germany) by means of the CASMO5 lattice physics code [1], developed by Studsvik Scandpower, for a representative fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 in order to assess a database of fuel inventories to be employed in the activities of the SASPAM-SA project. The calculation assumptions as well as the results of such evaluations are reported and discussed in the present document.

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1 Introduction

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are one of the advanced Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) to be deployed in the near-term worldwide. In Europe, the technological and economical interest for SMRs has been growing for some years. Activities are going on in several member states aiming at supporting the licensing of such systems. Among the different concepts, the Integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWRs) are of particular interest. They are ready to be licensed as new builds, since they integrate several evolutionary features, particularly of a passive nature, to enhance even further the already inherent safety. In spite of the advantageous impact of passive system on the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) approach, a systematic demonstration of iPWR ability to prevent and to manage Severe Accidents (SA) needs to be done (DiD levels 4-5)¹.

In order to fill this gap, the HORIZON-EURATOM 'Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accidents' (SASPAM-SA) project, coordinated by ENEA (Italy), was launched in 2022 and takes the contribution of 23 partners from 13 European countries [1-5]. The main objective of the SASPAM-SA project is to investigate the applicability and transfer of knowledge and know-how accumulated on the operating large-LWR reactors to the iPWRs. These activities are performed in view of European licensing needs relevant to SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) analyses. SASPAM-SA therefore aims at investigating the key elements to create a European independent point of view on the safety of iPWRs with respect to DiD levels 4 and 5. The expected project's outcome is to support and speed-up the licensing and siting process of iPWRs in Europe.

Four main elements, not addressed in other on-going SMR oriented initiatives, will be investigated:

- Identification of plausible postulated SA scenarios for iPWR designs;
- Identification of the conditions in the vessel and in the containment that characterize iPWR postulated SA scenarios and differ significantly from those in large-LWRs;
- Study the applicability of the existing experimental database to iPWR and identify new experimental needs;
- Assess the capability of internationally recognized European and Non-European computational tools (largely used in Europe) to describe the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site, taking into account SA special mitigation/management strategies.

The achievement of the overall elements is assured by a consistent and coherent work programme, reflected in the technical Work Packages (WP) structure (Figure 1).

In order to maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project two generic design-concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactor, have been selected for the analyses. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the project's

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied. More detailed information's in [7]. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the capability of internationally recognized SA code to describe the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site.

objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favoured designs under postulated SA condition.

Figure 1: Structure of SASPAM-SA project.

Despite generic, they resemble some of the features of currently discussed designs and take benefit from available data in the open literature and engineering assumptions when data are missing. The generic design considered are called Design 1 and Design 2:

- Design 1: iPWR characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe. The general layout of the iPWR Design-1 is shown in Figure 2.
- Design 2: iPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe. The general layout of the iPWR Design-2 is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Layout of the iPWR Design-1 generic reactor concept.

Figure 3: Layout of the iPWR Design-2 generic reactor concept.

2 The generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2

The generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 considered in the SASPAM-SA project are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The specifications of both designs were determined in the WP2 based on open literature and engineering judgment [7]. Such generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features considered in the most promising designs in the European market. Therefore, their employment in the project aims to assess more broadly the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR.

The generic IPWR Design-1 reactor here investigated consists of a natural circulation iPWR composed of a shrouded reactor core and riser, an integrated Pressurizer (PRZ), and Helical coil Steam Generators (HSGs) within an integral RPV housed inside a steel containment. The containment is largely immersed in a large pool of water, serving as the Ultimate Heat Sink (UHS). The Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) in the iPWR Design-1 consists of two groups of valves allowing the coolant circulation between RPV and containment during accident conditions: the Reactor Vent Valves (RVV) located at the top of the PRZ and Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRVs) located slightly above the active core².

The IPWR Design-2 Figure 3 is characterized by the use of several passive systems³ and by a dry containment. The reactor operates in forced circulation during normal operation and employs a passive mitigation strategy

² Even though Design-1 is generic, it includes some of the more evolutionary features of advanced SMR concepts, as integral RPV, compact SG, and natural circulation primary/containment coupling. More information about these features can be found in [8].

³ Passive systems are, on the one hand, an advanced solution to increase the inherent safety of the plant (e.g., there is no need of pumps), on the other hand a) they require extensive investigation for assessing the functional failure related to the thermal-hydraulic phenomena driving the operation of the systems and assess the related uncertainties, b) may still need an active initiation, and c) are characterized by very limited operational experience (to have more detailed information [1,9]). Considering this, the impact of the operation of passive systems on postulated SA progression is a novel topic and needs to be assessed. Considering this, the specific assessment of the code capability to simulate passive systems phenomenology is crucial. In fact, in LW-SMR reactors the BDBA/SA scenarios evolution depend from the postulated partial or total not operation of passive systems (e.g., postulate the failure of passive system valve activation). Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the capability of SA codes to predict the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena involved in the passive mitigation strategy of LW-SMR in order to adequately apply them for the design of

in accidental conditions. It consists of an integral RPV, containing the core, HSGs, primary pumps, the Control Rod Drive Mechanism (CRDM), and the PRZ. The hot water at the core outlet flows upwards in a circular riser up to the primary pumps suction located above each HSGs⁴.

As mentioned above, the objective of SASPAM-SA is not the assessment of the selected generic iPWR designs. On the contrary, the goal of the project is to investigate and proof the applicability of the state-of-art computation tools to reproduce SA conditions in generic iPWRs and identify code development needs.

3 WP2 – SCENARIOS – DESCRIPTION

The objective of the WP2, “Input deck development and hypothetical SA scenarios assessment (SCENARIOS)” coordinated by KIT (Germany), is the development of generic but representative iPWR SA code input-decks and the analysis of the iPWR behaviour under hypothetical postulated SA conditions. As said before, two generic designs concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations, will be considered. In order to fulfil the goals, the following tasks will be addressed:

- Development of plant models using different SA codes for iPWR Designs 1 and 2, including the estimation of the nuclide inventory for plausible radiological ST prediction;
- Identification of plausible postulated SA sequences for the iPWR Designs 1 and 2;
- Simulation of selected postulated SA-sequences for iPWR Designs 1 and 2 using different SA-codes, covering the in-vessel, the ex-vessel (if any), and the containment phenomena;
- The capability of the codes to model ATFs will be investigated with the support of code developers;
- The effect of the employment of the ATFs on the progress of the analysed SA scenarios (RPV failure, hydrogen production, ST, etc.) in the iPWR designs will be investigated. The public data available from the QUENCH ATF-related experiments performed at KIT will be employed.

One of the tasks of this WP is the estimation of the nuclide inventory for realistic radiological ST prediction. This task will be divided in the following sub-tasks:

- Collection of the detailed public information of core loadings of the iPWR Designs 1 and 2;
- Assessment of the corresponding core models for neutronic codes, e.g., KORIGEN, SCALE, Serpent;
- Prediction of the nuclear inventory for the beginning, the middle, and the end of the irradiation cycle (BOC, MOC, and EOC, respectively) to be employed in the SA-codes analyses for the estimation of the radiological ST and EPZs in case of hypothetical SA in iPWRs.

In the next sections the main results of this task are discussed. A milestone titled “iPWR Design 1 and Design 2 Inventory vs. Burn-up (w/o ATF)” is coupled with this deliverable.

accident management’s strategy (first phase of a SA is only dominated by thermal-hydraulic phenomena, then in-vessel is affected by thermal-hydraulic phenomena). Since the aim of the activity is to test the capability of the codes in reproducing the behavior of different passive safety systems and their interaction in a SMR configuration, in order to analyze code capability in a wider way the following passive systems have been considered for the design 2: passive decay heat removal; primary automatic depressurization; passive high-pressure safety injection; containment pressure suppression; passive low-pressure safety injection; flooding of the Reactor Cavity (RC).

⁴ Considering the selected passive systems and the generic iPWR features, acknowledging that our Design 2 is a generic design, a generic IRIS-SMR type has been considered as reference for this analysis (no proprietary data have been used); therefore, the main geometric information has been determined by scaling the data available from the SPES-3 facility [10], by engineering evaluation or public general data available from the IRIS reactor [11].

4 Fuel

Efforts have been spent to assess a database of fuel inventories at different burn-up states for the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 in the framework of the activities planned in the Task 2.3 of the WP2 (SCENARIOS) of the SASPAM-SA project.

The amount of Fission Products (FPs) in the core is one of the key parameters driving the progression and the radiological consequences of a hypothetical postulated SA in a NPP. The larger is the mass of the FPs, the larger is the decay power, which triggers the accident after the reactor scram. As a result, larger portions of in-vessel materials degrade faster, triggered by the higher temperatures in the core, also in conjunction with the loss of in-vessel cooling. Such hypothetical postulated scenarios lead to larger FP release from the vessel to the containment and then to the environment due to the higher-pressure conditions reached in the containment zones. Therefore, the assessment of a plant model in SA codes should employ realistic fuel inventories for a reliable evaluation of the ST during a SA scenario.

Having this in mind, depletion calculations have been performed for a representative 2D fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 and a database of fuel inventories composed of 300 isotopes has been assessed. With this goal, the CASMO5 lattice physics code [1], developed by Studsvik Scandpower, has been employed to evaluate the evolution of the fuel inventory of both systems from 20 MWd/kgU to 60 MWd/kgU, with a burn-up step of 2.5 MWd/kgU.

In the next, the modelling options for CASMO5 calculations will be described. Furthermore, the 2D CASMO5 models of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 will be shown and the results with respect to the evolution of the mass of 300 isotopes as well as of the corresponding activity (in Bq) during the burn-up will be shown.

5 –Modelling options employed in the CASMO5 depletion calculations

CASMO5 is the state-of-art 2D lattice physics code of Studvisk Scandpower, which is employed for modelling square and hexagonal fuel in light water reactors [12]. The code allows performing 2D neutron and gamma transport calculations in a lattice via the Linear Source Method of Characteristics (MOC) for two-dimensional heterogeneous geometries. The code employs a refined 586 energy-group structure, the ENDF/B-VII.1 neutron data library [13] being used, and the characteristics-based Dancoff method for the treatment of the neutron cross-section resonance self-shielding. The 586-group flux spectrum is employed to condense the neutron cross sections to a suitable structure for the 2D neutron transport calculations.

Concerning the depletion calculations, the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method is employed for solving the Bateman system of equation. Furthermore, the quadratic gadolinium depletion model is employed, where Gd-absorption rates are assumed to vary over the depletion step.

In order to assess the database of the fuel inventories at different burn-up states of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2, the CASMO5 depletion calculations for each system have been performed based on the following assumptions and calculation options:

- a 2D fully reflected fuel assembly as representative of the full core has been modelled;
- the P0 transport approximation has been employed in the lattice calculations;
- depletion calculations have been performed at full power from 20 MWd/kgU to 60 MWd/kgU with a step of 2.5 MWd/kgU, the upper limit being set based on [14];
- no cooling times have been modelled;
- the boron concentration in the water has been set the same for the whole depletion calculation;

- the transport calculations are performed by employing the 19-broad energy-group structure shown in Table 1 (default option for UO₂ fuel) obtained by collapsing the 586-fine energy-group structure.

Table 1: 19 energy group-structure employed in the CASMO5 calculations.

Group	Upper limit	Lower limit	Width	Unit
1	20	4.9659	15.0341	MeV
2	4.9659	1	3.9659	MeV
3	1	0.0193	0.98069	MeV
4	19.305	5.5308	13.7742	keV
5	5.5308	0.1487	5.3821	keV
6	148.7	47.9	100.8	eV
7	47.9	27.7	20.2	eV
8	27.7	16	11.7	eV
9	16	6.825	9.175	eV
10	6.825	6.525	0.3	eV
11	6.525	4	2.525	eV
12	4	2	2	eV
13	2	0.625	1.375	eV
14	0.625	0.35	0.275	eV
15	0.35	0.3	0.05	eV
16	0.3	0.19	0.11	eV
17	0.19	0.1	0.09	eV
18	0.1	0.03	0.07	eV
19	0.03	0.00001	0.02999	eV

6 Assessment of the fuel inventory database for the iPWR Design-1 and Design- 2

For both the generic designs a standard fuel of 17 x 17 is considered. In the next two sub-sections the assessment of the fuel inventory database is discussed in detail for both the designs.

6.1 Assessment of the fuel inventory database for the iPWR Design-1

The geometrical data of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1 are provided in Table 2. The geometry arrangement of a standard fuel of 17x17 Westinghouse fuel assembly has been considered [15][16]. In order to enhance synergies among European projects related to safety, it is essential to consider the significant contributions made by the MCSAFER project [17]. Considering this and acknowledging that Design 1 is a generic design, we take the data generated by the MCSAFER project as a reference point. With this in mind, it is considered that the core is loaded with with 256 UO₂ and 8 UO₂+Gd₂O₂ fuel rods [17].

Table 2. Geometrical data of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel rod array	17x17	-	[15][16]
Fuel rod pitch	12.6	mm	[15][16]
No. fuel rods/assembly	264		[17]
No. of guide Thimbles	24		[15][16]
No. of instrumentation tubes	1		[15][16]
Fuel pellet OD	8.2	mm	[15][16]
Cladding material	Zr	-	[17]
Cladding OD	9.5	mm	[15][16]
Cladding ID	8.3	mm	[15][16]
Cladding thickness	0.6	mm	[15][16]
Fill gas	He	-	[15][16]

The CASMO model of the fuel assembly is shown in Figure 4, where the UO_2 and the $UO_2+Gd_2O_2$ fuel rods as well as by 25 guide tubes, are labelled in green, red, and light blue, respectively.

Figure 4: CASMO5 model of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1.

The properties of the UO_2 and $UO_2+Gd_2O_2$ fuel rods are provided in Table 3 and

Table 4, respectively.

Table 3. Properties of the UO_2 fuel pellets.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel material	UO_2	-	[15][16]
U5 enrichment	4.95	wt.%	[15][16]
Uox density	10.97	g/cm ³	[15][16]
Fuel density, % TD	96.0	%	[15][16]

Table 4. Properties of the UO₂+Gd₂O₂ fuel pellets.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel material	UO ₂ +Gd ₂ O ₂	-	[17]
U5 enrichment	4.95	wt.%	[17]
Gd enrichment	2.75	wt.%	[17]
UO ₂ +Gd ₂ O ₂ density	10.53	g/cm ³	[17]
UO ₂ +Gd ₂ O ₂ density, % TD	96.00	%	[17]

The CASMO5 transport calculations have been performed by setting the boundary conditions shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Boundary conditions for the CASMO5 depletion calculations.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel Temperature	1000	K	[17]
Clad Temperature	650	K	[17]
Water Temperature	600	K	[17]
Water pressure	128	bar	[17]
Boron concentration	2000	ppm	[17]
Power density	58.46	kW/l	Calculated

The behaviour of the k-infinite during the burn-up is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1: k infinite versus burn-up.

The rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU) and of the ²³⁵U enrichment (wt.%) in the fuel assembly at 20 MWd/kgU are shown in Figure 6. Similarly, the results at 60 MWd/kgU are shown in Figure 7. As expected, larger burn-up values are observed at the centre of the fuel assembly and close to the water rods. In particular the maximum burn-up is 21.31 MWd/kgU and 62.78 MWd/kgU at the two depletion states here considered.

19.73	19.36	19.35	19.51	19.72	19.86	19.81	19.7	19.62
19.36	19	19.01	19.41	19.95	20.52	19.99	19.8	17.93
19.35	19.01	17.17	20.4	21.03	0	20.74	20.63	0
19.51	19.41	20.4	0	21.31	21.08	20.36	20.29	20.79
19.72	19.95	21.03	21.31	20.93	21.1	20.43	20.36	20.88
19.86	20.52	0	21.08	21.1	0	20.97	20.94	0
19.81	19.99	20.74	20.35	20.42	20.97	20.42	20.4	20.95
19.69	19.78	20.61	20.27	20.34	20.92	20.39	20.4	20.93
19.59	17.9	0	20.75	20.84	0	20.93	20.92	0

3.06	3.09	3.09	3.07	3.05	3.04	3.05	3.06	3.07
3.09	3.12	3.12	3.08	3.03	2.98	3.03	3.05	2.98
3.09	3.12	3.05	2.99	2.94	0	2.96	2.97	0
3.07	3.08	2.99	0	2.91	2.93	3	3	2.96
3.05	3.03	2.94	2.91	2.95	2.93	2.99	3	2.95
3.04	2.98	0	2.93	2.93	0	2.94	2.94	0
3.05	3.03	2.96	3.0	2.99	2.94	2.99	2.99	2.94
3.06	3.05	2.97	3.0	3.0	2.94	2.99	2.99	2.94
3.07	2.99	0	2.96	2.95	0	2.94	2.94	0

Figure 6. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1: rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU, left) and of the U²³⁵ enrichment (wt.%, right) at 20 MWd/kgU.

59.25	58.4	58.47	58.78	59.24	59.53	59.53	59.48	59.52
58.4	57.66	57.9	58.58	59.78	60.95	59.93	59.83	58.78
58.47	57.9	57.05	61.01	62.21	0	61.46	61.35	0
58.79	58.58	61.02	0	62.78	62.1	60.67	60.57	61.59
59.26	59.8	62.22	62.78	62.02	62.17	60.81	60.66	61.68
59.55	60.97	0	62.11	62.17	0	61.87	61.78	0
59.55	59.95	61.47	60.67	60.81	61.87	60.78	60.71	61.82
59.48	59.82	61.34	60.55	60.64	61.77	60.71	60.7	61.76
59.49	58.74	0	61.53	61.62	0	61.79	61.74	0

0.98	1.01	1.01	0.99	0.97	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95
1.01	1.04	1.03	0.99	0.94	0.88	0.93	0.94	0.88
1.01	1.02	0.96	0.88	0.83	0	0.85	0.86	0
0.99	0.99	0.88	0	0.8	0.82	0.89	0.9	0.85
0.97	0.94	0.83	0.8	0.84	0.82	0.88	0.89	0.84
0.95	0.88	0	0.82	0.82	0	0.83	0.84	0
0.95	0.93	0.85	0.89	0.88	0.83	0.89	0.89	0.84
0.95	0.94	0.86	0.9	0.89	0.84	0.89	0.89	0.84
0.96	0.88	0	0.85	0.85	0	0.84	0.84	0

Figure 7. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1: rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU, left) and of the U²³⁵ enrichment (wt.%, right) at 60 MWd/kgU.

In order to compute the isotope-mass wise during the burn-up, the iPWR Design-1 has been considered to be loaded by about 37 fuel assemblies with an active height of about 2.0 m, according to the data in [17].

The isotope-wise masses computed by means of CASMO5 at each burn-up step are provided in Table A-1. In order to compute the isotope-wise activity, the specific activity for each isotope has been calculated based on the decay data in the ENDF/B-VII.1 library [13]. The corresponding results (in Bq/kg) are shown in Table A-2. Finally, the evolution of the isotope-wise activity (in Bq) during the depletion calculations has been computed, the results being provided in Table A-3.

The behaviour of the total mass of heavy metals during the burn-up from 20 to 60 MWd/kgU is shown in Figure 8. Furthermore, the evolution of the total masses of noble gases, I, Cs, Ba, and Gd are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8. iPWR Design-1: total mass of the heavy metals in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 9. iPWR Design-1: total mass of the Kr, I, Xe, Cs, Ba, and Gd in the core vs. burn-up.

The activity in the core of selected isotopes having a relevance on the source term are shown in the following. Concerning the selected Iodine isotopes, the results in Figure 10 show that their contribution to the total activity in the core is about 1-2% as well as for contribution of ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , and ^{138}Cs shown in Figure 11. Concerning the Xe isotopes, the results in Figure 12 show that the contribution to the total activity is about 2%. Similar results are observed for ^{139}Ba , ^{89}Sr , and ^{91}Sr (Figure 13) and for ^{92}Y , ^{97}Zr , and ^{131}Te (Figure 14).

Figure 10. iPWR Design-1: total and Iodine isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 11. iPWR Design-1: total and Cesium isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 12. iPWR Design-1: total and Xenon isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 13. iPWR Design-1: total, ^{139}Ba , ^{89}Sr , and ^{91}Sr activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 14. iPWR Design-1: total, ^{90}Y , ^{92}Y , ^{97}Zr , and ^{131}Te activity in the core vs. burn-up.

6.2 Assessment of the fuel inventory database for the iPWR Design-2

The geometrical data of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2 are provided in Table 6 and the CASMO5 model is shown in Figure 15⁵.

Table 6. Geometrical data of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel rod array	17x17	-	[11] [16]
Fuel rod pitch	13.3	mm	[11] [16]
No. fuel rods/assembly	264		[11] [16]
No. of guide thimbles	24		[11] [16]
No. of instrumentation tubes	1		[11] [16]
Fuel pellet OD	8.2	mm	[11] [16]
Fuel active length	4.2	m	[11]
Cladding material	Zr	-	[11] [16]
Cladding OD	9.5	mm	[11] [16]
Cladding ID	8.36	mm	[11] [16]
Cladding thickness	0.57	mm	[11] [16]
Diametral Gap	0.16	mm	[11] [16]
Fill gas	He	-	[11] [16]

The fuel assembly is a 17x17 array loaded with 264 UO₂ and by 25 guide tubes, labelled in green and light blue in Figure 15, respectively.

Figure 15: CASMO5 model of the fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2 [19].

⁵In order to develop the integral code input-deck, a reference database was needed. Considering the characteristics of Design 2 reactor type and the selected passive systems, a generic IRIS SMR type has been considered as reference for this analysis. During the SA code development nodalization of the generic IRIS design, no proprietary data have been used; therefore, the main geometric information has been determined by scaling the data available from the SPES-3 facility [10,21], by engineering evaluation or public general data available for the IRIS reactor [11]. The plant specifications and design details have been collected in [7].

The properties of the UO₂ fuel rods are provided in Table 7 and the boundary conditions for the CASMO5 depletion calculations are shown in Table 8.

Table 7. Properties of the UO₂ fuel pellets.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel material	UO ₂	-	[11] [16]
U5 enrichment	4.95	wt.%	[11] [16]
UOx density	10.97	g/cm ³	[11] [16]
Fuel density, % TD	96.00	%	[11] [16]

Table 8. Boundary conditions for the CASMO5 depletion calculations.

Data	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel Temperature	1000	K	[17]
Clad Temperature	650	K	[17]
Water Temperature	600	K	[17]
Water pressure	155	bar	[11]
Boron concentration	1200	ppm	[17]
Power density	51.55	kW/l	Calculated

The behaviour of the k-infinite during the burn-up is shown in Figure 16, the results showing a good agreement with similar evaluations performed in [21]

Figure 16. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2: k infinite versus burn-up.

The rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU) and of the ²³⁵U enrichment (wt.%) in the fuel assembly at 20 MWd/kgU are shown in Figure 17. Similarly, the results at 60 MWd/kgU are shown in Figure 18.

19.05	18.88	18.94	19.11	19.3	19.45	19.43	19.45	19.49
18.89	18.78	18.96	19.27	19.72	20.26	19.79	19.78	20.24
18.96	18.97	19.51	20.4	20.83	0	20.56	20.51	0
19.17	19.32	20.44	0	21.14	20.87	20.18	20.12	20.62
19.44	19.85	20.93	21.2	20.78	20.91	20.24	20.17	20.69
19.76	20.55	0	21.01	20.97	0	20.76	20.71	0
20.07	20.44	21.04	20.45	20.37	20.8	20.23	20.2	20.69
20.76	21.55	21.58	20.57	20.35	20.78	20.22	20.2	20.71
21.5	21.56	0	21.17	20.89	0	20.71	20.71	0

3.07	3.08	3.08	3.06	3.04	3.03	3.03	3.03	3.02
3.08	3.09	3.07	3.04	3	2.95	3	3	2.95
3.07	3.07	3.02	2.94	2.9	0	2.92	2.93	0
3.05	3.04	2.93	0	2.87	2.89	2.96	2.96	2.92
3.03	2.99	2.89	2.86	2.9	2.89	2.95	2.96	2.91
3	2.92	0	2.88	2.88	0	2.9	2.91	0
2.97	2.93	2.88	2.93	2.94	2.9	2.95	2.96	2.91
2.9	2.83	2.83	2.92	2.94	2.9	2.95	2.96	2.91
2.83	2.83	0	2.86	2.89	0	2.91	2.91	0

Figure 17. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2: rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU, left) and of the U²³⁵ enrichment (wt.%, right) at 20 MWd/kgU.

57.86	57.5	57.66	58.06	58.49	58.81	58.8	58.84	58.91
57.52	57.27	57.69	58.36	59.41	60.45	59.58	59.58	60.42
57.73	57.74	58.94	60.72	61.66	0	61.07	60.97	0
58.24	58.51	60.81	0	62.33	61.69	60.44	60.33	61.21
58.87	59.74	61.89	62.45	61.74	61.82	60.61	60.43	61.38
59.57	61.12	0	62.01	61.96	0	61.53	61.43	0
60.28	60.99	62.11	61.05	60.91	61.64	60.6	60.53	61.39
61.71	63.14	63.16	61.31	60.88	61.62	60.59	60.56	61.45
63.04	63.14	0	62.37	61.85	0	61.45	61.46	0

0.88	0.89	0.88	0.86	0.83	0.81	0.82	0.81	0.81
0.89	0.89	0.87	0.83	0.79	0.74	0.78	0.78	0.74
0.88	0.87	0.81	0.72	0.68	0	0.70	0.71	0
0.85	0.82	0.72	0	0.65	0.67	0.73	0.74	0.69
0.81	0.77	0.67	0.64	0.67	0.66	0.72	0.73	0.69
0.77	0.70	0	0.65	0.66	0	0.68	0.68	0
0.74	0.70	0.65	0.70	0.71	0.67	0.72	0.73	0.68
0.67	0.61	0.60	0.68	0.71	0.67	0.72	0.72	0.68
0.61	0.61	0	0.64	0.66	0	0.68	0.68	0

Figure 18. Fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-2: rod-wise distribution of the burn-up (MWd/kgU, left) and of the U²³⁵ enrichment (wt.%, right) at 60 MWd/kgU.

As expected, larger burn-up values are observed at the centre of the fuel assembly and close to the water rods. In particular, the maximum burn-up is 21.58 MWd/kgU and 63.16 MWd/kgU at the two depletion states here considered.

In order to compute the isotope-mass wise during the burn-up, the iPWR Design-2 has been considered to be loaded by 89 fuel assemblies with an active height of 4.2 m, according to the data in [11].

The isotope-wise masses computed by means of CASMO5 at each burn-up step are provided in Table B-1. Finally, the evolution of the isotope-wise activity (in Bq) during the depletion calculations has been computed by employing the specific activities in Table A-2, the results being provided in Table B-2.

The behaviour of the total mass of U and minor actinides during the burn-up from 20 to 60 MWd/kgU is shown in Figure 19 and the evolution of the total masses of Xe, Kr, I, Cs, Ba, and Gd are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 19. iPWR Design-2: total mass of the heavy metals in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 20. iPWR Design-2: total mass of the Kr, I, Xe, Cs, Ba, and Gd in the core vs. burn-up.

The activity in the core of selected isotopes having a relevance on the source term are shown in the following. Concerning the selected Iodine isotopes, the results in Figure 21 show that their contribution to the total activity in the core is about 2-3%, while the contribution of ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , and ^{138}Cs is about 1%, as shown in Figure 22. Concerning the Xe isotopes, the results in Figure 23 shows that the contribution to the total activity is about 1-2%. Similar results are observed for ^{139}Ba , ^{89}Sr , and ^{91}Sr (Figure 24) and for ^{92}Y , ^{97}Zr , and ^{131}Te (Figure 25).

Figure 21. iPWR Design-2: total and Iodine isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 22. iPWR Design-2: total and Cesium isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 23. iPWR Design-2: total and Xenon isotopes activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 24. iPWR Design-2: total, ^{139}Ba , ^{89}Sr , and ^{91}Sr activity in the core vs. burn-up.

Figure 25. iPWR Design-2: total, ^{90}Y , ^{92}Y , ^{97}Zr , and ^{131}Te activity in the core vs. burn-up.

7 Conclusions

Depletion calculations have been performed at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in order to assess a database of fuel inventories of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2. The work has been performed in the framework of the Task 2.3 of the WP2 (SCENARIO). The calculations have been carried out by using the CASMO5 lattice code, developed by Studsvik Scandpower, in order to evaluate the evolution of the fuel inventory of both systems from 20 MWd/kgU to 60 MWd/kgU, with a burn-up step of 2.5 MWd/kgU.

A database containing the evolution of the mass and of the activity of 300 isotopes has been assessed in view of their employment in the analysis of hypothetical severe accident scenarios by means of integral codes.

The database also represents a preliminary step for the activities planned in the WP5 (CONT), focused on the assessment of the code capabilities to simulate iPWR containment and characterize mitigation measures efficiency, and in the WP6 (EPZ), focused on the characterization of the iPWR Emergency Planning Zone.

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Dy163	0.000E+00	1.382E-02	1.921E-02	2.569E-02	3.333E-02	4.219E-02	5.233E-02	6.383E-02	7.676E-02	9.118E-02	1.072E-01	1.248E-01	1.442E-01	1.654E-01	1.884E-01	2.134E-01	2.405E-01	2.696E-01
Dy164	0.000E+00	1.806E-03	2.804E-03	4.129E-03	5.828E-03	7.945E-03	1.052E-02	1.361E-02	1.724E-02	2.145E-02	2.629E-02	3.179E-02	3.798E-02	4.490E-02	5.259E-02	6.107E-02	7.038E-02	8.054E-02
Dy165	0.000E+00	3.867E-07	6.105E-07	9.117E-07	1.306E-06	1.810E-06	2.438E-06	3.207E-06	4.136E-06	5.241E-06	6.541E-06	8.056E-06	9.804E-06	1.180E-05	1.407E-05	1.664E-05	1.950E-05	2.270E-05
Ho165	0.000E+00	5.044E-04	8.942E-04	1.484E-03	2.337E-03	3.525E-03	5.129E-03	7.239E-03	9.956E-03	1.339E-02	1.765E-02	2.286E-02	2.917E-02	3.671E-02	4.561E-02	5.605E-02	6.816E-02	8.212E-02
Gd152	4.643E-01	2.743E-01	2.537E-01	2.343E-01	2.161E-01	1.990E-01	1.831E-01	1.682E-01	1.542E-01	1.412E-01	1.291E-01	1.179E-01	1.074E-01	9.776E-02	8.881E-02	8.056E-02	7.295E-02	6.597E-02
Tb162	0.000E+00	9.362E-09	1.008E-08	1.073E-08	1.140E-08	1.211E-08	1.285E-08	1.363E-08	1.444E-08	1.530E-08	1.619E-08	1.711E-08	1.808E-08	1.907E-08	2.010E-08	2.116E-08	2.225E-08	2.335E-08
Dy166	0.000E+00	1.795E-08	2.795E-08	4.145E-08	5.911E-08	8.167E-08	1.099E-07	1.447E-07	1.870E-07	2.377E-07	2.979E-07	3.687E-07	4.512E-07	5.467E-07	6.562E-07	7.810E-07	9.224E-07	1.081E-06
Ho166	0.000E+00	2.636E-07	4.775E-07	8.059E-07	1.290E-06	1.978E-06	2.927E-06	4.201E-06	5.873E-06	8.028E-06	1.076E-05	1.416E-05	1.836E-05	2.346E-05	2.961E-05	3.692E-05	4.556E-05	5.566E-05
Ho166m	0.000E+00	6.070E-07	1.153E-06	2.027E-06	3.350E-06	5.265E-06	7.939E-06	1.156E-05	1.633E-05	2.248E-05	3.027E-05	3.994E-05	5.179E-05	6.612E-05	8.323E-05	1.034E-04	1.271E-04	1.545E-04
O-16	1.238E+03																	
O-17	5.010E-01	5.011E-01	5.012E-01	5.012E-01	5.012E-01													
O-18	2.862E+00	2.863E+00																
Total	10706.2																	

Table A-2. Specific activity (Bq/kg).

Isotope	Bq/kg												
Th230	7.6335E+11	Am241	1.2705E+14	Kr85	1.4493E+16	Rh104	2.2452E+21	Te123	1.7949E+02	Ce139	2.5269E+17	Gd159	3.9482E+19
Th231	1.9666E+19	Am242	2.9901E+19	Kr87	1.0491E+21	Rh105	3.1258E+19	Te127	9.7720E+19	Ce141	1.0547E+18	Gd161	1.1857E+22
Th232	4.0601E+06	Am243	7.3890E+12	Kr85m	3.0481E+20	Rh107	2.9989E+21	Te129	7.7543E+20	Ce143	2.4557E+19	Tb160	4.1783E+17
Pa231	1.7488E+12	Am244	4.7038E+19	Rb86	3.0166E+18	Pd107	1.9048E+10	Te131	2.1258E+21	Ce144	1.1783E+17	Tb161	4.3472E+18
Pa232	1.5894E+19	Am242m	3.8782E+14	Rb87	3.0937E+06	Pd109	7.7708E+19	Te132	1.1431E+19	Pr142	4.2734E+19	Dy165	3.0121E+20
Pa233	7.6877E+17	Am244m	1.0963E+21	Sr89	1.0754E+18	Pd111	2.6807E+21	Te127m	3.4927E+17	Pr143	2.4913E+18		
U232	8.2793E+14	Cm242	1.2260E+17	Sr90	5.1137E+15	Ag110	6.2760E+21	Te129m	1.1154E+18	Pr144	2.7976E+21		
U233	3.5678E+11	Cm243	1.8714E+15	Sr91	1.3244E+20	Ag111	5.8473E+18	I128	2.1765E+21	Nd144	4.0165E+01		
U234	2.3037E+11	Cm244	2.9963E+15	Y90	2.0120E+19	Ag112	3.3103E+20	I129	6.5403E+09	Nd147	2.9950E+18		
U235	7.9992E+07	Cm245	6.3543E+12	Y91	9.0831E+17	Ag110m	1.7600E+17	I130	7.2214E+19	Nd149	4.5058E+20		
U236	2.3943E+09	Cm246	1.1301E+13	Y92	3.5638E+20	Cd109	9.6147E+16	I131	4.6014E+18	Nd150	1.3177E-02		
U237	3.0194E+18	Cm247	3.4342E+09	Zr93	9.3118E+10	Cd113	1.5225E+01	I132	3.8302E+20	Nd151	3.7055E+21		
U238	1.2445E+07	Cm248	1.5332E+11	Zr95	7.9499E+17	Cd115	1.8876E+19	I133	4.1943E+19	Pm146	1.6404E+16		
U239	1.2410E+21	Bk249	5.8779E+16	Zr96	6.9006E-03	Cd117	3.9832E+20	I134	9.8959E+20	Pm147	3.4343E+16		
U240	3.4256E+19	Cf249	1.5140E+14	Zr97	7.1456E+19	Cd118	1.1731E+21	I135	1.3082E+20	Pm148	6.0846E+18		
Np235	5.1893E+16	Cf250	4.0466E+15	Nb94	6.9434E+12	In115	2.6121E+02	I136	4.4155E+20	Pm149	1.4669E+19		
Np236	3.6413E+11	Cf251	5.8575E+13	Nb95	1.4548E+18	In116	1.8115E+22	Xe133	6.9333E+18	Pm150	2.8859E+20		
Np237	2.6044E+10	Cf252	1.9852E+16	Nb96	5.1776E+19	In117	1.3776E+21	Xe135	9.4036E+19	Pm151	2.7052E+19		
Np238	9.5868E+18	Ge76	9.0523E-05	Nb97	9.9570E+20	Sn121	3.5480E+19	Xe136	4.4985E-05	Pm148m	7.9104E+17		
Np239	8.5763E+18	Ge77	1.3339E+20	Nb98	5.2121E+23	Sn123	3.0425E+17	Xe137	1.3309E+22	Sm147	8.4996E+05		
Np240	4.6819E+20	As76	5.9041E+19	Mo99	1.7778E+19	Sn125	4.0123E+18	Xe135m	3.3727E+21	Sm148	1.2784E+01		
Np236m	2.1832E+19	As77	3.8821E+19	Mo100	1.8660E-02	Sn126	4.5708E+11	Cs134	4.7873E+16	Sm151	9.7450E+14		
Pu236	1.9621E+16	As78	9.8437E+20	Mo101	4.7189E+21	Sn127	4.3507E+20	Cs135	4.2659E+10	Sm153	1.6306E+19		
Pu237	4.5091E+17	Se79	5.6855E+11	Tc98	3.2189E+10	Sn123m	1.4130E+21	Cs136	2.7012E+18	Sm155	2.0137E+21		
Pu238	6.3402E+14	Se81	4.6600E+21	Tc99	6.3395E+11	Sn125m	5.8506E+21	Cs137	3.2049E+15	Sm156	7.9110E+19		
Pu239	2.2966E+12	Se82	1.6658E-03	Tc100	1.6736E+22	Sb122	1.4550E+19	Cs138	1.5099E+21	Eu154	1.0007E+16		
Pu240	8.4003E+12	Se83	3.7624E+21	Tc101	4.8553E+21	Sb124	6.4770E+17	Ba139	6.0298E+20	Eu155	1.7945E+16		
Pu241	3.8265E+15	Br82	4.0098E+19	Tc102	1.4692E+23	Sb125	3.8416E+16	Ba140	2.7079E+18	Eu156	2.0398E+18		
Pu242	1.4582E+11	Br83	5.8268E+20	Ru103	1.1958E+18	Sb126	3.1070E+18	La138	9.4099E+05	Eu157	4.8675E+19		
Pu243	9.6255E+19	Br84	2.6071E+21	Ru105	2.4893E+20	Sb127	9.8882E+18	La140	2.0578E+19	Eu158	9.5974E+20		
Pu244	6.7792E+08	Kr81	7.1433E+11	Ru106	1.2211E+17	Sb128	1.0061E+20	La141	2.0991E+20	Gd153	1.3142E+17		

Dy165	0.000E+00	1.165E+14	1.839E+14	2.746E+14	3.935E+14	5.451E+14	7.342E+14	9.660E+14	1.246E+15	1.579E+15	1.970E+15	2.426E+15	2.953E+15	3.555E+15	4.239E+15	5.011E+15	5.875E+15	6.836E+15
Ho165	0.000E+00																	
Gd152	3.746E+02	2.213E+02	2.046E+02	1.890E+02	1.743E+02	1.606E+02	1.477E+02	1.357E+02	1.244E+02	1.139E+02	1.042E+02	9.509E+01	8.667E+01	7.886E+01	7.165E+01	6.499E+01	5.886E+01	5.322E+01
Tb162	0.000E+00	5.293E+13	5.699E+13	6.063E+13	6.444E+13	6.844E+13	7.264E+13	7.704E+13	8.165E+13	8.648E+13	9.151E+13	9.675E+13	1.022E+14	1.078E+14	1.136E+14	1.196E+14	1.258E+14	1.320E+14
Dy166	0.000E+00	1.537E+11	2.394E+11	3.549E+11	5.062E+11	6.994E+11	9.413E+11	1.239E+12	1.601E+12	2.035E+12	2.551E+12	3.157E+12	3.864E+12	4.681E+12	5.619E+12	6.689E+12	7.899E+12	9.259E+12
Ho166	0.000E+00	6.873E+12	1.245E+13	2.101E+13	3.364E+13	5.159E+13	7.632E+13	1.095E+14	1.531E+14	2.093E+14	2.805E+14	3.693E+14	4.787E+14	6.118E+14	7.719E+14	9.627E+14	1.188E+15	1.451E+15
Ho166m	0.000E+00	4.035E+07	7.668E+07	1.348E+08	2.227E+08	3.500E+08	5.277E+08	7.683E+08	1.086E+09	1.495E+09	2.012E+09	2.655E+09	3.443E+09	4.395E+09	5.532E+09	6.876E+09	8.449E+09	1.027E+10
O-16	0.000E+00																	
O-17	0.000E+00																	
O-18	0.000E+00																	
Total	1.145E+12	1.896E+19	1.923E+19	1.941E+19	1.960E+19	1.978E+19	1.997E+19	2.015E+19	2.034E+19	2.053E+19	2.072E+19	2.091E+19	2.110E+19	2.129E+19	2.148E+19	2.167E+19	2.186E+19	2.205E+19

Dy164	0.000E+00	4.669E-04	5.848E-04	7.186E-04	8.687E-04	1.036E-03	1.221E-03	1.426E-03	1.651E-03	1.897E-03	2.165E-03	2.456E-03	2.772E-03	3.112E-03	3.479E-03	3.874E-03	4.298E-03	4.752E-03
Dy165	0.000E+00	1.443E-07	1.875E-07	2.277E-07	2.742E-07	3.277E-07	3.891E-07	4.593E-07	5.395E-07	6.307E-07	7.340E-07	8.507E-07	9.820E-07	1.129E-06	1.294E-06	1.476E-06	1.679E-06	1.903E-06
Ho165	0.000E+00	4.221E-04	5.544E-04	7.140E-04	9.049E-04	1.131E-03	1.398E-03	1.711E-03	2.074E-03	2.496E-03	2.982E-03	3.539E-03	4.177E-03	4.902E-03	5.725E-03	6.653E-03	7.697E-03	8.867E-03
O-16	6.371E+03	6.372E+03	6.373E+03	6.373E+03	6.373E+03	6.373E+03												
O-17	2.579E+00	2.580E+00																
O-18	1.473E+01	1.474E+01																
Total	5.512E+04																	

Dy165	0.000E+00	4.347E+13	5.647E+13	6.858E+13	8.258E+13	9.869E+13	1.172E+14	1.384E+14	1.625E+14	1.900E+14	2.211E+14	2.562E+14	2.958E+14	3.401E+14	3.896E+14	4.447E+14	5.058E+14	5.732E+14
Ho165	0.000E+00																	
O-16	0.000E+00																	
O-17	0.000E+00																	
O-18	0.000E+00																	
Total	6.056E+12	8.590E+19	9.279E+19	9.397E+19	9.493E+19	9.589E+19	9.685E+19	9.784E+19	9.885E+19	9.988E+19	1.009E+20	1.020E+20	1.031E+20	1.042E+20	1.053E+20	1.065E+20	1.076E+20	1.087E+20